

INFLUENCE OF TALENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION IN PRIVATE HOSPITALS IN NAIROBI CITY COUNTY: A CASE OF THE NAIROBI HOSPITAL

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Abstract: Employee retention and talent management concerns are quickly becoming the most pressing workforce management challenges of the near future as human resource management paradigms shift. This study was on Private hospitals which are health organizations formed and owned by individuals or organizations to provide health services to citizens. The general objective of this study was to establish the influence of talent management on employees' retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County. Specifically, the objectives were to establish whether talent acquisition, talent development, employee performance and staff deployment influence employee retention in the private hospitals in Nairobi City County from the lenses of Nairobi Hospital which was the case study. The study adopted descriptive design, a case study where the target population comprising of all the employees in the hospital was used. The respondents were all permanent and pensionable employees and contract-based employees from all departments in Nairobi Hospital. In addition, human resource director was part of the respondents. Stratified sampling was used to select the respondents from different categorization of the hospital. A self-administered questionnaire was used as the main tool for data collection and was administered to a total of 168 respondents. Reliability of the study questionnaire was tested using Cronbach's alpha coefficient which was found to be above 0.7 hence reliable. To measure the validity of research, content validity was used where experts scrutinized the questionnaire and found to be valid. The researcher analyzed data using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Statistical software (SPSS version 26) was used. The findings from these statistics were presented in the form of tables. Inferential statistics in the form of factor and principal component analysis was also conducted. The inferences made were used to tell apart the major factors that influenced employee turnover in private hospitals particularly the case of Nairobi hospital in Nairobi City County. The findings found out that, talent acquisition, talent management, employee performance and staff deployment significantly influenced employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County but to moderate extent. Therefore, recommendations focused on working on the maturity of employees, improving the working conditions as well as fostering the leadership. Future research should focus on determining specific factors that influence retention in institutions to assist companies deal with similar situations

Keywords: Talent Acquisition, Talent Development, Employee Performance, Staff Deployment, Employee Retention.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Globalization has raised competitiveness while also opening up new doors of opportunity for organisations. According to Gallardo, Thunnissen, and Scullion, (2020) posit that the current global economic scenario has enhanced the importance of talent management and employee retention. Hanief (2013), stated that intellectual capital is always a valuable asset for any firm in which they must invest. People, intellectual capital, and talent are becoming increasingly important to an

organization's strategic success. According to Armstrong (2009), talent management has been viewed to revolve around putting the appropriate individuals with the right abilities in the right roles and at the right time. Talent management is the systematic acquisition, identification, development, engagement, and retention of those employees who are valuable to an organisation, either because of their "high potential" for the future or because they are performing business/operation-critical jobs (CIPD, 2013)

Today, the demand for competent individuals is considerable, particularly for critical decision-making workforce; as a result, firms are exposed to a continuous competitive war for the best and most talented employees. Indeed, there is a paradigm shift from human resource to human capital, which consists of the knowledge, skills, and capacities of the people engaged in an organisation that are indicative of their value (Armstrong, 2010). Today, major corporations face the difficulty of keeping their talent as they compete in global marketplaces (Sculer et al, 2011; Scullion et al, 2010, Tarique & Schuler, 2010). In this "battle for talent," firms must reduce turnover in order to retain talented personnel (McDonnell, 2010). The primary goal of talent management is to keep competent individuals from leaving the organisation, which could have a negative impact on performance and service delivery (Ng'ethe, Iravo, & Namusonge, 2012). Research indicates that companies doing best of managing their talent deliver better results (Abdi, Omwenga, & Guyo, 2020). The identification and development of internal high-potential employees is referred to as 'talent management within the human resource function (Nyanjom, 2013). Talent management is actions taken by organizations for the purpose of attracting, selecting, developing, and retaining the best employees in most strategic roles which in turn leads to better employee performance (Scullion & Collings, 2011). It aims at developing the right people in the right jobs at the right time, ensuring the right environment for individuals to deliver their best and remain committed to the organization (Uren & Jackson, 2012). According to Chartered Institute of Professional Development (CIPD, 2013) talent consists of those individuals who can have influence on organizational performance either through their immediate contribution or, in the longer-term, by demonstrating the highest levels of potential. The growth potential of organizations worldwide depends on the ability of companies to have the right people, in the right place at the right time.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Employee retention is one of the challenges facing many organizations both public and private (Chew, 2004; Ng'ethe, Iravo & Namusonge, 2012). Retention of talented employees has become an even greater challenge confronting human resource practitioners because talented candidates in the global job skills market have a luxury of choice. The increasing importance of talent management in the modern and competitive business world has initiated a need to focus on managing talent as an organization's competitive asset (Nyanjom, 2013). However, managing talent is a challenge to all organizations as they compete for the same pool of talents (Gardener, 2002; Kagwiria, 2014). The importance of talent management in state corporations in Kenya, for example is ensuring that they are future oriented, that is they have the right skills in place to be able to retain talent, grow and compete in the future that is increasingly unpredictable (Nana, 2013). Talent shortage is being experienced in every organization regardless of the industry because skills set possessed by available workers may not match the more complex advanced skills required by business (Buhler, 2008; Kagwiria, 2014). Nana (2013) suggests that organizations should ensure that they are better positioned to meet the problems of talent shortage.

Staff turnover has been regarded as a general degree or sign of the firm functionality. Once workers are disgruntled with their job, they tend to pull back to limit their presentation to the work. Worker renewal rate is further aggravated by the fact that dropping extraordinary accomplishing people affect the output of the firm, as the firm misses the venture that was made in their advancement. As the percentage of the workforce in the professional or highly technical work increases, understanding and effective management of the occupation affiliation amongst specialized personnel and their hiring firms turns out to be progressively essential (Cox, 2012). Disproportionate worker renewal rate generates unsteady personnel, escalates expenses, and impacts negatively on organizational performance.

Early studies in the nursing department in distinct parts of the world have seen turnover as a problem. For instance, a study by Burns and Grove in UK in 2001 explored the gap of knowledge required in the nursing practice and uncovered turnover as a major challenge. A similar study by Morrel (2005) in UK identified tremendous nurse shortage because of turnover. Lephalala (2003) study of turnover in England acknowledged that a lack of recognition, irregular promotions, inability to recognize autonomy as leading reasons for nurse turnover. Lephalala (2003) research also covered non-European countries as related results were determined.

Kenya has also conducted studies in both public and private hospitals regarding employee turnover. For instance, Ndemaki (2014) conducted a study to “determine the factors influencing turnover among doctors at the Aga Khan Hospital, Kisumu” where he found grouped the factors organizational, individual, environmental, and job-related factors. Another study was conducted by Omondi in (2010) to “determine the factors influencing turnover of medical doctors at the Nyanza provincial general hospital” where he identified environmental, job, individual and organizational factors as key influencers. In 2015, Ofunya Afande tried to determine the factors that contribute to the high turnover among nurses working in MP Shah were resulted confirmed both extrinsic and intrinsic factors as influential. With the identified factors that can influence turnover among doctors and nurses. Dr. Susan Lewa (2010) wrote a journal article on Talent Management and Forecasting in Kenya’s Higher Education Sector and concluded that managers’ capacity for talent management requires improvement and that the managers in public universities needed education and training on talent management dynamics.

From the previous paragraphs, the studies have been done on employee retention outside kenya different context from kenya. The one that have been done locally have concentrated on other sectors such as education. This present study seeks to identify the influence of talent management on employee retention in Private hospitals in Nairobi County, a case of The Nairobi hospital.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The study will be guided by the following objectives

1.3.1 General objective of the Study

The general objective of the study is to examine the influence of talent management systems on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

1.3.2 Specific objectives of the Study

1. To determine the influence of talent acquisition on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.
2. To examine the influence of talent development on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.
3. To find out the influence of employee performance on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.
4. To establish the influence staff deployment on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

1.4 Research questions of the Study

1. What is the influence of talent acquisition on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County?
2. To what extent talent development influence employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County?
3. How does employee performance influence employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County?
4. Is there any influence of staff deployment on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County?

1.5 scope of the study

The study was conducted in private hospitals in Nairobi City County because employee retention and talent management are a pertinent issue raised other studies. The study focused on talent management and employee retention. The study used these variables to evaluate the influence of Talent management in private hospitals in Nairobi City County. Talent acquisition, talent development, employee performance and staff deployment. The study will use a case of The Nairobi hospital. It will address the top, middle level managers and section heads to answer questions as both supervisors and employees of the hospital.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This study will be anchored on two theories which are Herzberg’s two factors theory and human capital theory.

2.1.1 Herzberg Two Factor Theory

Herzberg’s two factors theory was created by Frederick Irving Herzberg in 1950 as part of the pleasures of motivation theories. The model believes that the motivation to work is intrinsic rather than external. To attain an internal drive to work, a firm must create a conducive environment such as encouraging self-realization, delegation of responsibilities,

offering status to employees and offering an enabling environment through favorable policies, working conditions, and supervisions. Even though external motivators such as salaries and rewards influence the motivation to work, Herzberg theory insists that working atmosphere has a higher contribution towards workers' satisfaction (Murrells, Robinson, & Griffiths, 2008). The motivator factors emphasize on non-monetary stimuli such as achievement recognition, decision making involvement in addition to other intrinsic conditions (Murrells, et al., 2008).

External conditions that facilitate the standards of an individual include job security, fringe benefits, salary increment, and allowances. For such, companies are entitling to make sure that they establish and re-establish conditions externally oriented practices that encourage employee involvement (Holmberg, Sobis, and Carlstrom, 2015). The model is beneficial to this study as it gives a perspective about the needs to employees to ensure a favorable working condition which can nurture their talents. Emerging factors that the concept presents are that there is an inverse relationship between interior and exterior motivations. Therefore, employees will not be able to offer their best when they are not involved in a company's affairs. To inspire the desire to work, employees must understand the external and internal influences of workers' capacity to work (Murrells, Robinson, & Griffiths, 2008). The model is helpful as the management will know how to incorporate the employees in daily affairs of the organisations to make them feel valued and not left out and thus remain loyal to the organization.

2.1.2 Human Capital Theory

The theory was developed in 1964 by Becker and postulates that human capital is useful in the process of production and directly increases productivity in a range of tasks. The theory asserts that skilled/educated workforce enables a firm to implement new and advanced technologies thus strengthening returns on training and education. Human capital is grounded in individual talents, training, and experience. Bartel and Borjas (1977) asserts that since there is limited economic value available in the alternative settings from specific human capital, outcomes that are efficient may be realized only if returns and costs of investments from specific human capital are shared between employees and the firm.

Sutherland (2004) notes that large amount of value of an organization is in possession of employees and when competent employees exit companies, they carry with them this value. It is indeed the abilities, skills and knowledge of individuals that create value, which necessitates focus to be directed on the means of developing, retaining, attracting, and maintaining the human capital they represent. This theory supports the variables of career management and training because it is crucial for the employees to realize their line of career within the hotel which will motivate them to realize their personal goals by remaining in the organization.

2.2 Conceptual framework

Figure 2. 1 conceptual framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

According to Cooper and Schindler (2014), research design constitutes the outline for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data. It expresses both the structure of the research problem, which consists of the framework, organization, or configuration of the relationships among variables of a study and the plan of investigation used to obtain realistic evidence on those relationships. This study will adopt cross sectional research design because its purpose is to produce an accurate representation of persons, events, or situations.

3.2 Target Population

According to Cooper and Schindler (2003), a population is the total collection of elements about which we wish to make inferences. The population of the study included non-clinical and clinical staff employed by The Nairobi hospital either on contract or permanent and pensionable terms. The total number of these staff is 570 (Nairobi hospital, 2019). The employees employed on casual and temporary terms are likely to leave the organization. The total population is broken down into categories as shown in the next section in table 3.1

3.3 Sample size and sampling frame

A sample is a subset of the population. A sample in this study was a portion of the population of interest. The purpose of sampling is to secure a representative group which will enable the researcher to gain information about a population. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), social researchers recommend that 10% - 30% of the accessible population is enough, and at least thirty cases are required per group, for statistical data analysis. If a population from which a sample is to be drawn does not constitute a homogenous group, a stratified sampling technique is applied to obtain a representative sample. Stratified sample results in a more reliable and detailed information. Stratified random sampling using designation will be used in the first stage to ensure representation of the subgroups constituting health workers in the Nairobi Hospital. In the second stage, simple random sampling will be used to arrive at the required sample of 30% of the target population. The sampling frame is as shown in table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1: target population and sample size

Type of staff	Target population	Sample size
Medical officers and specialists	46	13
Dentists	10	3
Pharmacists	18	6
Nurses	180	54
Clinical officers	13	4
Lab techs	28	8
Pharm technologists	10	3
Radiographers	10	3
Nutritionists	12	4
Physiotherapists	18	6
Occupational therapists	12	4
Medical record officers	17	5
Public health officers	4	1
Other professional staff	200	60
Total	570	168

Source (The Nairobi hospital, 2019)

3.4 Data collection instruments

This study used primary data which was collected using questionnaires. The questionnaires had closed ended questions in line with the objectives of the study. The choice of the method is on the premise that data collected using a questionnaire is easily understood and therefore perceived as authoritative. Additionally, using questionnaire provide greater control over the research process.

3.5 Data collection procedure

The questionnaires were distributed to respondents by the researcher using a drop and pick approach. Respondents were assured of anonymity by giving questionnaires unique numbers instead of respondents' name. Only the researcher understood the codes on the questionnaires, hence ensuring respondent confidentiality. A clear explanation was given to respondents as to how they could benefit from the research. This was done to ensure a high response rate

3.6 Pilot test

A pilot study was undertaken for pre-testing the questionnaire. The questionnaire was then edited in the light of the results of the pilot study. According to Kothari, (2004), the pilot study reveals the weakness of the questionnaire if any. The researcher conducted a case study of the Karen Hospital. Piloting enabled the researcher to ascertain the validity and reliability of the instrument. Validity is the extent to which a scale or set of measures accurately represents the concept of interest. Only five employees of the Karen hospital were used for pilot testing.

3.6.1 Validity

Validity is the most critical criterion and indicates the degree to which an instrument measures what it is supposed to measure (Kothari, 2004). According to Gay (1992), validity is established by expert judgment. In this regard, the questionnaire was constructed in close consultation with the university supervisor and other experts.

3.6.2 Reliability

According to Kothari (2004), Reliability of the information gathering instrument is the consistency of estimation and every now and again evaluated utilizing a test-retest dependability technique. Cooper and Schindler (2010) further demonstrated that a pilot test is directed at identifying shortcomings in plan and instrumentation and to give intermediary information to the choice of a likelihood test. Cronbach alpha of 0.863 was obtained which was above the required 0.7. This shows that the instrument was reliable.

Table 3.2: Reliability test results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.863	5

3.7 Data Analysis

Before processing the responses, data preparation was done on the completed questionnaires by editing, coding, entering, and cleaning the data. The study used quantitative method of data analysis. To ensure effective analysis, the questionnaire was coded according to each variable of the study to ensure the margin of error is minimized as to assure accuracy during analysis. The quantitative analysis was applied using descriptive statistics. According to Denscombe (1998), descriptive statistics involves a process of transforming a mass of raw data into tables with frequency distribution, mean and standard deviation, which are a vital part of making sense of the data. Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26.0 program and presented using tables to give a clear understanding of the research findings. Inferential statistics makes inferences about populations using data drawn from the population. Inferential statistics correlation analysis was used to determine the effect of talent management systems and their influence on employee retention.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Response rate

The respondents who participated in the study were non-clinical and clinical staff employed by The Nairobi hospital either on contract or permanent and pensionable terms. The respondents filled and returned the questionnaires as indicated in Table 4.1

Table 4.1: Response rate

	Frequency	Percentage
Response	155	92.3
Non-response	13	7.7
Total	168	100

Table 4.1 indicates that the questionnaire return rate was 92.3 percent which is adequate for analysis. According to Mugenda, (2008), response rate above 70% is adequate for analysis

4.2 Descriptive statistics

4.2.1 Respondents' opinion on statements relating to talent acquisition and employee retention

This section sought to determine the opinion of the respondents on to what extent talent acquisition influenced their retention. Table 4.2 reflects that talent acquisition as a factor that influence employee retention had an aggregate mean of 3.36 and standard deviation of 1.073. This indicated that the respondents were clear of how talent acquisition affected employee retention in the hospital. The standard deviation of 1.073 however indicated that a consensus about the score was not arrived at. In respect to individual statements, respondents of the study were asked to indicate whether the level of agreement with the statement that Skills Audit is conducted to assess the skills gap in their organization. The results show that majority of the respondents agreed with a mean of 3.5419 and a standard deviation of 0.6954.

On the statement that the recruitment process provides for an extensive selection of talent question, majority agreed with a mean of 0.4129 and standard deviation of 1.9001 The study also wanted to know the level of respondent's agreement on the statement before a vacancy is advertised, effort is made to tap from the internal talent pool. The findings showed that the majority were undecided with a mean of 2.8710 and a standard deviation of 1.0550. When asked whether induction programs are well structured to help the new employees settle in, most respondents agreed with the statement with a mean of 3.438 and a standard deviation of 1.2118 Finally, many of the respondents agreed that there was sufficient pool of managerial talent available at Nairobi hospital to fill vacancies. This had a mean of 3.5613 with a standard deviation of 1.0134.

Table 4.2: respondents' opinion on talent acquisition

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
A Skills Audit is conducted to assess the skills gap	155	3.5419	.69543
The recruitment process provides for an extensive selection of talent	155	3.4129	1.39007
Before a vacancy is advertised, effort is made to tap from the internal talent pool	155	2.8710	1.05504
Induction programs are well structured to help the new employees settle in	155	3.4387	1.21187
There is sufficient pool of managerial talent available at Nairobi hospital to fill vacancies	155	3.5613	1.01344
Total aggregate	155	3.36	1.073

4.2.2 Respondents' opinion on statements relating to talent development and employee retention

Table 4.3 reflects that talent development a factor that stimulates employee retention had an aggregate mean of 2.507 and standard deviation of 0.962. This indicated that the respondents were undecided on how talent development influences employee retention in private hospitals. The standard deviation of 0.962 indicated that there was consensus about the score. In respect to individual statements that made up talent development the respondents agree that promotion in hospitals is not based on seniority but on performance with a mean of 3.5871. A standard deviation of 0.81214 meant respondents agreed about the rating. In addition, the respondents were undecided on the statement that targets, and their due date are clearly communicated to staff in their departments with a mean of 3.6452. Furthermore, this evaluation was unanimously agreed upon by all the respondents.

The respondents neither agreed nor disagreed on the statement that that the organization has mechanisms in place to ensure performance and feedback with mean 3.1935. The standard deviation 0.9885 indicated a consensus among the respondent's ratings. Similarly on the statement that staff in my department are provided with opportunities for growth and development, the respondent were neutral with a mean of 3.081 and a standard deviation of 0.98850.

Finally, the respondents unanimously disagreed that Performance reviews in their organization provides them with accurate information about their strengths, weaknesses, and development areas with a mean of 2.2452 and a standard deviation of 0.87045

Table 4.3: respondents' opinion on talent development

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Promotion in my organization is not based on seniority but on performance	155	3.5871	.81214
Targets and their due date are clearly communicated to staff in my department	155	3.6452	1.05524
The organization has mechanisms in place to ensure performance and feedback	155	3.1935	1.08769
Staff in my department are provided with opportunities for growth and development	155	3.0581	.98850
Performance reviews in my organization provides me with accurate information about my strengths, weaknesses, and development areas	155	2.2452	.87045
Total aggregate	155	2.507	0.962

4.2.3 Respondents' opinion on statements relating to employee performance and employee retention

Table 4.4 above reveals that employee performance system had a mean aggregate of 2.624 implying that the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed on how this system influenced employee retention in the hospital. The standard deviation of 1.287 showed that there was no harmony among the respondents while evaluating this system. While evaluating individual statement related to employee performance, respondents neither agree nor disagree that their organization always plans on employee career growth with mean of 2.5875. The 1.194 standard deviation suggests that the respondents were differed while evaluating the statement. On the same note the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed that employee career development programs offered in the organization are linked to each employee's career needs with 2.5613 mean. The 1.233 standard deviation showed that there was disharmony in the respondents' scores. The respondents also neither agreed nor disagreed that every effort is made to use skills or create capacity before with 2.813 mean. The standard deviation of 1.221 indicated that there was no uniformity when evaluating this factor. On the statement that the organization has in-house development programs to develop its employees, the respondents neither did they agree nor disagree with the mean of 2.7677. However, there was no harmony in evaluating this factor given the standard deviation of 1.210. The respondents on the other hand disagreed with the statement that employee career development benefits are in place in their organization with a mean of 2.3935.

Table 4.4: respondents' opinion on employee performance

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
The organization always plans on employee career growth	155	2.5871	1.19407
Employee career development benefits are in place in this organization	155	2.3935	1.58113
Employee career development programs offered are linked to each employee's career needs	155	2.5613	1.23311
Every effort is made to use skills or create capacity before outsourcing	155	2.8129	1.22096
My organization has in-house development programs to develop its employees.	155	2.7677	1.21045
Total aggregate	155	2.624	1.287

4.2.4 Respondents' opinion on statements relating to employee staff deployment and employee retention

Table 4.5(a) above indicates that the respondents agreed with the statement that their organization has systematic succession plans, enabling employees to effectively perform roles traditionally reserved for managers with the mean of 3.2129. The standard deviation of 1.06 shows that their uniformity on the way the respondents evaluated the statement. Regarding individual statements on wages and salary, the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed that they were fairly compensated on their position and their skills development with mean 3.67. The standard deviation 0.266 indicated agreements in the respondent's views. However, the respondents disagreed that they were compensated their salary in a timely manner with mean 2.42. The standard deviation 0.384 indicated that there was consensus among the respondents.

Table 4.5(a): respondents' opinion on staff deployment

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
My organization has systematic succession plans, enabling employees to effectively perform roles traditionally reserved for managers	155	3.2129	1.12231
My organization identifies and prepares suitable high potential employees to replace key players within the organization as their terms expire	155	3.1419	1.06563
My organization focuses on the promotion and development needs of subordinates	155	2.9419	1.29052
My organization has succession planning programs that strongly influences staff retention and employee performance	155	3.8323	.92455
Total aggregate	155	2.626	1.101

4.2.5 Opinion on employee retention

Table 4.5(b) indicates that the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed with total aggregated mean of 3.373 about employee retention. The standard deviation of 1.09 implied that the respondents rating was reached upon a consensus.

With respect to individual statements respondents neither agreed nor disagreed with a mean of 3.323 that they know what is expected of them at their workplace. The standard deviation of 0.97 shows that there was harmony in respondents' scores. In addition, the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed that someone at workplace has talked to them about the progress at the hospital in the last six months with a mean of 3.1677. The standard deviation of 0.9923 indicated a consensus among respondent's scores. However, the respondents agreed that they have materials and equipment to do their work right with the mean of 3.5484. The standard deviation of 1.233 shows that there was no consensus among the respondents when evaluating the statement.

The respondents were not decided on the statement that the mission or purpose of my company makes me feel my job is important with the mean of 3.29. There was consensus in respondents' evaluation indicated by the standard deviation of 1.04. Finally on the statement about recognition or praise for the work well done, the respondents agreed with a mean of 3.5484. There was also variation among respondents when evaluating the statement as shown by a standard deviation of 1.2337

Table 4.5(b): respondents' opinion on employee retention

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
I know what is expected of me at work	155	3.3226	.97325
In the last six months, someone at work has talked to me about my progress at the hospital	155	3.1677	.99230
I have the materials and equipment I need to do my work right	155	3.5484	1.23369
The mission or purpose of my company makes me feel my job is important.	155	3.2903	1.04427
In the last seven days, I have received recognition or praise for doing decent work	155	3.5484	1.23369
Total aggregate	155	3.3736	1.0954

4.3 Inferential statistics

4.3.1 Correlation Analysis

The study sought to establish the relationship between independent variables and dependent variable. The study indicates a correlation coefficient matrix that assesses the relationship between study variables (independent variables) themselves. The results are as shown in table 4.6. The result of the correlation shows that talent acquisition and employee retention correlates as shown by a correlation value of 0.521 and a p-value of 0.000. This means that the correlation is positive and significant implying that increase in reward systems leads to increase in employee retention in the hotel industry. The

findings are consistent with Ombui and Wambugu (2013) which revealed a positive correlation between talent management and work performance of employees.

The correlation results further indicates that the correlation between talent development and retention of employees is 0.623 and a p-value of 0.000. This means that the correlation is positive and significant implying that increase in talent development leads to increase in employee retention in private hospitals. The findings concur with Abok and Makwaro (2014) findings when investigating the factors that affected management of talent in state corporations and revealed factors such as career development, performance management, workforce environment and reward significantly affect talent management implementation.

The results also indicate that the correlation between employee performance and employee retention is 0.158 and a p-value of 0.000. This implies that the correlation is significant though minimal meaning that increase in talent management practices leads to slight increase in employee retention in private hospitals. The findings are consistent with Piansoongnern, Anurit and Kuiyawattananonta (2011) findings on their investigations on strategies on talent management and employee engagement which revealed that employee training, work life balance and support of management were crucial factors necessary for keeping talents rooted to organizations.

The correlation analysis results finally revealed that the correlation between staff deployment and employee retention is -0.450 and a p-value of 0.042. This means that the correlation is negative and significant implying that improvement on staff deployment leads to decreased retention of employees in private hospitals. The findings contradict with Mapelu and Jumah (2013) study which revealed that employee development positively and significantly correlated with employee turnover.

Table 4.6: Correlation analysis results

Correlations		Talent acquisition	Talent development	Employee performance	Staff deployment	Employee retention
Talent acquisition	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	155				
Talent development	Pearson Correlation	.329**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
	N	155	155			
Employee performance	Pearson Correlation	.228**	.015	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	.854			
	N	155	155	155		
Staff Deployment	Pearson Correlation	-.078	-.259**	.157	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.334	.001	.005		
	N	155	155	155	155	
Employee retention	Pearson Correlation	.521**	.623**	.158**	-.450**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.002	
	N	155	155	155	155	155

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.3.2 Coefficient of determination

The study adopted a multiple linear regression analysis to evaluate the statistical relationships between independent variables (talent acquisition, talent development, and employee performance and staff deployment) and dependent variable (employee retention). A confidence level of 99% ($\alpha = 0.01$) was used. The results in table 4.7 indicates existence of a relationship between talent acquisition, talent development, and employee performance and staff deployment and employee retention as shown by $R = .769$. R-square which is the coefficient of determination was 0.592 meaning that 59.2% of variation in retention of employees in private hospitals in Nairobi City County can be explained by talent acquisition, talent development, and employee performance and staff deployment

Table 4.7: model summary results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.769 ^a	.592	.581	.39743
a. Predictors: (Constant), staff deployment, Talent acquisition, talent management, employee performance.				

4.3.3 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Table 4.8 shows the results of ANOVA tests. According to the results, the overall model linking talent acquisition, talent development, and employee performance and staff deployment with employee retention was statistically significant. This is confirmed by comparing the F calculated value and the F critical value. The F calculated value (54.345) exceeds F critical value (2.5252) implying that the overall model is statistically significant

Table 4.8: ANOVA results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34.335	4	8.584	54.345	.000 ^b
	Residual	23.692	150	.158		
	Total	58.027	154			

a. Dependent Variable: employee retention

b. Predictors: (Constant), staff deployment, talent acquisition, talent development, employee performance.

4.4 Regression analysis

The results of coefficients of the model are presented in Table 4.9 The results shows that talent acquisition has a positive and significant influence on employee retention as shown by $\beta = 0.352$ and $\text{Sig} = 0.000 < 0.01$. This implies that a unit change in talent acquisition results to an increase of 0.439 units in employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County. The findings are consistent with Karemu, *et al* (2014), findings which revealed talent management strategies impact positively on the retention of doctors and nurses at Kenyatta National hospital in Kenya.

The model of coefficient results also indicates that talent development has a positive and significant influence on employee retention as shown by $\beta = 0.425$ and $\text{Sig} = 0.000 < 0.01$. This implies that a unit change in talent development the practice results to an increase of 0.425 units in employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County. The findings concur with Abok and Makwaro (2014) when investigating the factors that affected management of talent in state corporations and revealed factors such as career development, employee engagement, workforce environment and reward to significantly influence talent management implementation.

The model of coefficient additionally indicates that employee performance has a positive and significant influence on employee retention as shown by $\beta = 0.021$ and $\text{Sig} = 0.002 < 0.01$. This implies that a unit change in employee performance results to an increase of 0.021 units in retention of employees in Kenyan private hospitals in Nairobi City County. The findings are consistent with Piansoongnern, Anurit and Kuyawattananonta (2011) on its investigations on strategies on talent management and employee performance which revealed that employee training, work life balance and support of management were crucial factors necessary for keeping talents rooted to organizations.

The model of coefficient finally revealed that staff deployment has a positive and significant influence on employee retention as shown by $\beta = 0.316$ and $\text{Sig} = 0.000 < 0.01$. This implies that a unit change in the staff deployment results to an increase of 0.0296 units in retention of employees in Kenyan private hospitals in Nairobi City County. The findings concur with Mapelu and Jumah (2013) findings which revealed that employee development positively and significantly correlated with employee turnover.

The multiple regression model that was obtained is.

$$Y = 1.650 + 0.352 X_1 + 0.425 X_2 + 0.021 X_3 - 0.316 X_4$$

Table 4.9: Regression analysis results

<i>Coefficients^a</i>						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.650	.334		4.934	.000
	Talent acquisition	.339	.055	.352	6.182	.000
	Talent development	.497	.067	.425	7.458	.000
	Employee performance	.024	.063	.021	.383	.002
	Staff deployment	-.318	.055	-.316	-5.764	.000

a. Dependent Variable: employee retention

5. SUMMARY OF STUDY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the study

The summary of findings summarizes each of the findings under each of the objectives of the study. The study sought to assess the influence of talent management systems on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

5.1.1 Influence of talent acquisition on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

The results on talent acquisition revealed that there is significant relationship between talent acquisition and employee retention in private hospitals (.521, $p > 0.01$). This shows that talent acquisition is important for employee retention, but it influences employee retention to a moderate extent. The findings show that skill audit is conducted in the organizations before recruitment is done. It was also revealed that during recruitment process, there is extensive selection of the talent. It further revealed that there is sufficient pool of managerial skills to fill the vacancies.

5.1.2 Influence of talent development on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County

In line with objective two the study revealed that talent development influences employee retention at (.623, $p > 0.01$). This shows that talent development influences employee retention to a moderate extent. Moderate responses determined that talent development influenced employee retention to some extent as indicated by an aggregate mean of 2.507. These findings were supposed by the highest mean of 3.6452 in which most of the respondents indicated that their targets and due dates are communicated to them clearly. The lower mean of 2.245 similarly found out that the respondents were not comfortable with performance reviews as they did not provide them with accurate information about their strengths, weaknesses, and development areas the training that is given in their organization with.

5.1.3 Influence of employee performance on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County

In line with employee performance, the study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between employee performance and employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County at ($r = .158$, $p < 0.01$). From the findings, it can be summarized that employee performance influences employee retention but to a low extent. It can also be summarized that it was not clear whether the organization plans for career growth, career development is offered in organization and that every effort is made to create capacity before outsourcing. However, the respondents disagreed with the statement that employee benefits are in place.

5.1.4 Influence of staff deployment on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County

Finally, the study revealed that employee deployment influences employee retention at ($r = .218$, $p > 0.01$). This shows that employee deployment has a positive significance influence on employee retention however to a low extent. The study depicts that the hospitals have succession planning programs that strongly influences staff retention and employee performance. In addition to this, all the organizations have systematic succession plans, enabling employees to effectively perform roles traditionally reserved for managers. However, it was not clear whether the organization identifies and prepares suitable high potential employees to replace key players within the organization as their terms expire. The respondents were also undecided on the organization's focus on the promotion and development needs of sub-ordinates.

5.2 Conclusion

The conclusions drawn from this study are discussed as per the variables under study. The study had the following conclusions.

5.2.1 Influence of talent acquisition on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

The findings of the study led to conclusions that talent acquisition positively and significantly influence retention of employees in private hospitals in Nairobi City County. The study further established that practices such as skills audit, recruitment process for selection of talents, good induction process as well as sufficient pool of managerial talents to fill vacancies positively and significantly influence employee retention in private hospitals.

5.2.2 Influence of talent development on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

The study also concluded that talent development positively and significantly influences retention of employees in private hospitals in Nairobi City County. The study further established that practices such as promotion in hospitals based on seniority and clear communication of targets to employees positively and significantly influences employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County. However, most employees showed that performance reviews in hospitals did not provide employees with accurate information about their strengths, weaknesses, and development areas.

5.2.3 Influence of employee performance on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

From the findings, the study concludes that employees' performance positively and significantly influences employee retention in the private hospitals in Nairobi City County. The study further concluded that factors such as creation of capacity before outsourcing and in-house programs to develop employees is crucial in retaining staff.

5.2.4 Influence of staff deployment on employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

The study findings finally concluded that employee deployment positively and significantly influence employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi city county hotel industry in Kenya. The study further established that provision of enough skills development opportunities to employees, providing equal opportunities for advancement to employees positively and significantly influences employee retention in Nairobi City County. The following conclusion was made from the study based on the summary and findings: It was concluded that employee retention based on talent acquisition, talent development, employee performance and employee deployment was influenced moderately in the hospital. Talent development came top among the systems that retain employees in hospitals while employee performance was the least system that retains employees in private hospitals in Nairobi City County.

5.3 Recommendations

From the conclusion made in the above section, the study recommended that the hospital management should pay keen attention to these factors and how they play out in the hospital if they were to influence employee retention effectively. Recommendations were done according to study objectives

5.3.1 Recommendations on talent acquisition and employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi city county

The hospital management would also consider employing the older generation, put more emphasis in the factors for example leadership and workplace conditions

5.3.2 Recommendations on talent development and employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi city county

The study recommended better review system where proper feedback is given to employees at appropriate time. The review system should also be able to point out strengths and weakness of employees

5.3.3 Recommendations on employee performance and employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi city county

The study recommended that the hospitals to have a career path for their employees. There should be a clear succession plan. It was further recommended that the hospitals to exhaust internal resources before seeking services elsewhere.

5.3.4 Recommendations on staff deployment and employee retention in private hospitals in Nairobi city county

The study recommended on job training of junior employees as they prepare them for promotions to take over from the ones who retire. It also recommended continuous staff training equipping those skills to assume any role within the organization.

5.4 Suggestion for Further Research

Further research could be done to establish what other factors influence employee retention turnover in institutions. The study could include similar variables or more variables to be assessed. As such this research would help produce more solid confirmation of the precise factors that influence employee retention and at the same time or reduce the error term.

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